

Authors' response

Adaptive principles of weight regulation: Not sufficient, but perhaps necessary, for understanding obesity

Daniel Nettle¹, Clare Andrews² & Melissa Bateson³

Centre for Behaviour and Evolution & Institute of Neuroscience, Newcastle University, Newcastle, UK

1. To whom correspondence should be addressed: daniel.nettle@ncl.ac.uk; <https://www.staff.ncl.ac.uk/daniel.nettle>
2. clare.andrews@ncl.ac.uk; <http://bit.ly/clareandrews>
3. melissa.bateson@ncl.ac.uk; <https://www.staff.ncl.ac.uk/melissa.bateson/>

Abstract

We reflect on the major issues raised by a thoughtful and diverse set of commentaries to our target article. We draw attention to the need to differentiate between ultimate and proximate explanation; the IH needs to be understood as an ultimate-level argument, though we welcome the various suggestions made about proximate mechanisms. Much of this response is concerned with clarifying the inter-relationships between adaptationist explanations like the IH, constraint explanations, and dysfunction explanations, in understanding obesity. We also re-examine the empirical evidence base, concurring that it is equivocal and only partially supportive. Several commentators offer additional supporting evidence, whilst others propose alternative explanations for the evidence we reviewed, and suggested ways that our current knowledge could be strengthened. Finally, we take the opportunity to clarify some of the assumptions and predictions of our formal model.

R1. Introduction

We are grateful to our commentators for engaging with our target article and providing thought-provoking responses. In what follows, we discuss each of the major groups of issues raised. In many cases, these inter-connect. The issues are varied. Some commentaries review additional sources of supportive evidence that we did not include in the target article. Some raise issues that turn on misapprehensions of what we claimed, misapprehensions that can be sorted out by defining terms and clarifying levels of analysis. Others still fill in ideas about proximate mechanisms, an issue not covered in our target article. Several commentaries offer alternative accounts of the empirical evidence we reviewed, or draw attention to its limitations. Finally, many of the most difficult issues raised involve understanding how the IH relates to other, possibly better-known, explanatory approaches to obesity. The IH stems from reasoning about the normal functioning of evolved weight-regulation mechanisms. How does this articulate with literatures that see obesity as a metabolic dysfunction, or over-eating as a failure of self-control? We have not been able to answer every point of detail, but have endeavoured to cover to the overarching or recurrent themes.

R2. Proximate and ultimate explanations

A useful distinction can be made between ultimate and proximate explanations for a phenotypic or behavioural pattern (Scott-Phillips, Dickins, & West, 2011; Tinbergen, 1963). Ultimate explanations are based on how the phenotypic or behavioural pattern contributes to survival and reproduction,

and hence offer an account of why that particular pattern has been retained over generations as part of the organism's phenotypic repertoire. For example, for trees in temperate latitudes, having full leaves in winter is disadvantageous because the photosynthetic yield from foliage at this time of year is insufficient to outweigh the cost of maintaining the foliage, and the increased likelihood of weather damage when a tree is in full leaf. Thus, many temperate trees have evolved a deciduous pattern; they grow full leaves in spring and drop them in autumn, thus balancing the benefits of photosynthesis when there is more sunshine and the costs of having leaves when there is not. This is an ultimate-level explanation. Likewise, the IH as we present it in the target article is an ultimate-level hypothesis; it seeks to explain why, in terms of benefits to evolutionary fitness, individuals might maintain higher fat reserves under conditions of insecurity than under conditions of security. Ultimate-level explanations are vital for explaining the ecological patterning of a phenotype in a satisfactory way.

Proximate explanations deal with the mechanisms by which the behaviour or phenotypic pattern of interest is triggered. In general, there are many possible (and perhaps non-exclusive) proximate mechanisms that could deliver any given ultimate-level function. For example, some deciduous trees are cued to sprout leaves by day length, whilst others are cued by temperature; two different proximate mechanisms for achieving the same ultimate function. Importantly, the proximate explanation need not involve the organism representing, at any level, what the ultimate function of the pattern is. Trees do not need to know or represent why it is they sprout leaves in spring in order to do so effectively. Rather, ancestral trees that sprouted leaves in spring and dropped them in autumn, however that was caused, have more descendants living today than trees that did not. Often, an ultimate function is delivered by a varied suite of different mechanisms operating in concert and with considerable redundancy; this is known to be true, for example, of animal navigation (Frost & Mouritsen, 2006).

Whilst behavioural biologists debate the limits to which functional explanation can be pursued independently of understanding mechanisms and vice versa (Fawcett, Hamblin, & Giraldeau, 2013; McNamara & Houston, 2009), all agree that an explanation in terms of a proximate mechanism is not an alternative to an explanation in terms of an ultimate function. This is important in the current case. For example, **Mullan et al** point out that people's immediate motivations for eating are often to do with taste and pleasure, rather than gaining calories. This is quite true, but to include taste and pleasure in our formal model on the same basis as evolutionary fitness would be to confuse proximate and ultimate levels of analysis. The ultimate function of eating is to obtain energy and nutrients; the proximate mechanisms by which our evolved brains do this include making food tasty and eating pleasurable. These two statements are both true, but not alternatives to one another. Similarly, 'culture' and 'diet' (**Lozano**) are not alternatives to the IH, but pathways through which food insecurity could affect body weights. **Ert and Heiman** suggest that the findings of the empirical literature on food insecurity and body weight could be explained by the IH, but could equally well be explained by changes to temporal discounting, or the feeling of scarcity brought on by food insecurity. Ert and Heiman describe these as "alternative psychological mechanisms" to the IH. However, we didn't propose any psychological mechanisms in the target article, so these obviously cannot be alternative ones! Rather than temporal discounting or the feeling of scarcity being alternatives to the IH, they could be part of a suite of psychological mechanisms that delivers increases in energy intake relative to expenditure under conditions of food insecurity, as the IH requires.

Our target article did not go into the question of proximate mechanisms at all, a fact that many commentators picked up on. We concur with them that the issue of proximate mechanisms is of critical importance. Its intentional absence was explained by limitations on what can be covered in one article. As behavioural ecologists often do, we began our enquiry from considering ultimate payoffs, and hence determining the kinds of strategies that one would expect to see emerging via natural selection (and the commentary by **Mattei** extends this strategic logic). We did so in a way

that was agnostic about the mechanisms by which weight regulation is actually achieved. This agnostic opening gambit does not mean we deny the existence or importance of such mechanisms. Understanding mechanism is crucial not only for a complete understanding of how something works. It also has particular relevance to understanding how phenotypes become maladapted. To return to our trees example, under rapid global warming, trees that use a temperature-based mechanism to cue coming into leaf will become progressively maladapted to actual patterns of available solar radiation (they will sprout leaves earlier and earlier), whilst trees that use day length will remain adapted. We thus fully concur with **Higginson, McNamara and Dall** that exploring the (no doubt multiple) mechanisms individuals have evolved to extract information from their environment about future energy need and energy availability will be critical to understanding why average body masses have become so unprecedentedly high in many modern populations, and why they become extremely high in some individuals (and, in eating disorders, extremely low in others, **Nesse**). Understanding proximate cues also offers possibilities for understanding how it might be possible to intervene to change outcomes, short of changing the whole ecology of society (**Cardel et al., Petit and Spence**). Ultimate understanding can only be a starting point for these kinds of enquiry; where a phenotype becomes maladapted, you also need to understand the interaction between evolved mechanisms and current environmental inputs.

R3. Varieties of proximate mechanism

DeJesus and **Wells** suggested that the IH implies that humans consciously reason about the probability of future shortfall and the resulting need to carry fat reserves. We were surprised by this, as the target article makes no such claim, and the claim strikes us as implausible. If mice and greenfinches can solve problems of weight regulation under intermittent food supply (presumably) without the need for conscious reasoning, it would be strange to assume that humans require conscious reasoning to achieve the same ends. The problem may lie with the term ‘decision-making’ that we used; for us this does not imply conscious deliberation, or even necessarily the involvement of the brain. It simply describes any kind of mechanism that maps some information from the environment onto some kind of phenotypic output. It may have different connotations for others, so we are glad to clarify.

On a related note, **Bentley and O’Brien** argue that the IH belongs to the class of explanations in the Northwest corner of their explanation-space. This is the quadrant where decisions are made individually by reasoning agents to whom the payoffs of the different alternatives are transparent. We don’t agree with this characterisation. The IH no more requires the payoffs for storing more fat to be transparent to the mind than the existence of tanning requires that melanocytes can represent the payoffs to having a lighter or darker skin. In fact, in Western populations, there probably are no payoffs to carrying more fat when food insecure, transparent or otherwise. Rather, the IH contends that there are evolved mechanisms that, when presented with particular types of cue, respond with changes to food motivation and/or energy expenditure that result in more fat storage. They respond in this way because ancestors who responded in this way to ancestral food insecurity have left more descendants than ancestor that lacked this response.

But what, then, can we say about the proximate mechanisms likely to be involved? We will not repeat at length the useful discussions on potential mechanisms by **DeJesus, Petit and Spence, Coppin, Blackwell, Ambroziak** and others. We agree that there are likely to be multiple, largely unconscious and automatic pathways by which experiences that in ancestral environments predicted the likelihood of future food shortfall, lead to increases in food consumption, shifts in food preference, and possibly changes in energy expenditure. The mechanisms may well alter the appraised or experienced pleasure and reward value of food, particularly of those sub-types of food that are most dense in energy. We also welcome **Ambroziak’s** reminder that the mechanisms must also involve an individual’s assessment of their own current bodily state, an assessment that can be inaccurate, for example in the case of eating disorders. There may be a special role for the

hypothalamic–pituitary–adrenal (HPA) axis (**Blackwell**). Hunger is associated with increased HPA activity (Erickson, Drevets, & Schulkin, 2003). Regular experience of serious hunger would thus become encoded in the individual in the form of frequent glucocorticoid stress responses, and *ex hypothesi* such a pattern would cause a shift in appetite. Indeed, there is good evidence, including experimental evidence (Tataranni et al., 1996), for the existence of this pathway (see Epel, Lapidus, McEwen, & Brownell, 2001).

A consequence of the existence of this HPA mechanism would be that anything other than food insecurity that caused a frequent glucocorticoid stress response would also have the potential to produce weight gain. There is widespread evidence for psychosocial stress promoting weight gain, as several of our commentators (e.g. **DeJesus, Blackwell, Smith**) point out. These associations can be seen as by-products of the glucocorticoid stress response being part of the mechanism that stores extra energy in response to food insecurity. Essentially, all kinds of stressful experience, that in contemporary environments do not predict, or only very weakly predict, future food scarcity, evoke mechanisms whose evolved function was to deal with food scarcity.

Chen and Dittman and Maner discuss the possible role of childhood in setting adult body weight. They link the IH to a body of recent work arguing that childhood experience provides the developing person with information about the adult world into which they will mature, and hence sets them on a path towards developing the appropriate phenotypic strategy for that world. We agree with these commentators that this possibility would not be incompatible with the IH but an extension of it; and that there is a large body of correlational evidence linking childhood psychosocial adversity with high adult body weight or altered eating (see Danese & Tan, 2014 and section 7.1 of target article). From an evolutionary point of view, the difficulty with these arguments is that given that food availability is likely to have fluctuated over short timescales in ancestral environments, it is hard to see how it could be adaptive to use childhood experience as information about food availability in the adult world that an individual will experience only years later. **Wells** has made this point forcefully (Wells, 2007), and repeats it in his commentary here (see also Nettle, Frankenhuys, & Rickard, 2013). Retaining full plasticity into adulthood would appear to be enormously superior from an adaptive point of view over canalisation during childhood, and indeed, fat reserves can change quite dramatically in adulthood. To solve this issue is beyond the scope of this paper. It may be that there are mechanistic or developmental constraints on adult plasticity that help explain why this should be the case, when using information from the adult environment would seem more beneficial.

Several commentators (**DeJesus, Mata et al**) point out eating is a social activity, and therefore food consumption is influenced by a number of different social processes. We fully agree. Again, we would not see social determination as conceptually an alternative to the IH. It is not just that social factors such as power, wealth and status determine food insecurity. It is that the mechanisms by which individuals extract information about their food ecology and food needs may include cues provided, passively or actively, by others. (For this reason, just as we do not agree that the IH resides in the North of the explanation space discussed by **Bentley and O'Brien**, we do not agree that it resides in the West either.) Whilst the existence of social transmission is not an alternative to the IH at the conceptual level, it does make the epidemiological predictions more complex. For example, as **Mata et al** point out, if some individuals buffer others from the effects of food insecurity, then we may fail to find associations where the theory predicts they should exist (e.g. perhaps in the case of children). If the perception of food insecurity is transmitted socially from person to person, then, even if this is basically an adaptive mechanism, there can be considerable non-adaptive cultural momentum. Eating patterns can perpetuate in particular social groups for a long time even if the initiating ecological conditions have been removed, and they can diffuse through networks not just to individuals who are actually food insecure, but to their secure associates too. These kinds of momentums and inertias arising from social transmission have been extensively discussed in the cultural evolution literature (Colleran, 2016; Richerson & Boyd, 2005).

R4. Constraint versus adaptationist explanations

The IH as discussed in the target article is an adaptationist hypothesis. That is, it attributes higher body weights in food-insecure social groups to the operation of evolved adaptive mechanisms for weight regulation. Note that adaptationist does not mean adaptive; if the current environment is sufficiently different from those over which the mechanism evolved, then the output of the mechanism will not maximize current fitness, even if the mechanism is functioning normally and has evolved through natural selection.

Several commentators proposed alternative explanations for the observed evidence, based instead on some kind of psychological constraint. For example, **Sacco** and **Dohle and Hofmann** invoke the idea that people with adverse lives may be too depleted or overloaded to exert the self-control needed to avoid overeating in an affluent environment, and **Wells** relatedly suggests that poverty reduces the agency required to resist commercial interests. (Wells refers to this as a reverse-causation argument to the IH, which it is not; the causality is in the same direction as in our argument, but via a different pathway to the one we proposed.) Rather than seeing these proposals as just proximate mechanisms delivering the ultimate function specified by the IH, we see them as arguments of a different kind. They characterise the consumption decisions of food-insecure people as, fundamentally, errors arising from not having the psychological capacity available to make better decisions (i.e. arising from psychological constraints). This is different from seeing them as automatic decisions that would have been beneficial, under the given environmental cues, in ancestral environments (i.e. arising from adaptations).

Constraint explanations are often invoked to explain the behaviour of the poor, though there are alternative adaptationist interpretations of the same phenomena (Nettle, 2010; Pepper & Nettle, 2016). We admit it can be challenging empirically to distinguish between the predictions of the two classes of explanation. We make several observations. The idea there exists some kind of domain-general self-control or self-regulatory capacity in humans that can get depleted is contested, and may not be well supported by evidence (Carter, Kofler, Forster, & McCullough, 2015; Kurzban, 2016). A number of experiments have attempted to experimentally deplete self-control to examine the impact on food consumption, and the average effect in these studies does not clearly differ from zero (Carter et al., 2015). Second, even if such a general self-control capacity did exist, it is not clear how much of the variation in people's body weights it would explain. Only a subsection of population reports using effortful restraint to control their eating, and this subsection tends to have *higher*, not lower, body weights than those who describe their eating as unrestrained (Rudermann, 1986). Thus, having greater resources for effortful restraint or self-control does not seem a promising avenue for explaining why more people in the most privileged social groups remain thin.

Related to constraints explanations are the widespread argument that the growth of obesity is explained by the marketing of sugar and fast food (mentioned here by **Bentley and O'Brien, Mullan et al**). But this is not in itself an explanation; one would also need to explain why people are susceptible to such marketing, and, in particular, why more insecure social groups appear to be more susceptible than others. Deeper principles are needed to explain such differential susceptibility, as **Smith** points out. The IH offers an alternative way of interpreting such differential susceptibility to ideas about constraints on self-control or agency.

R5. Dysfunction versus adaptationist explanations

Wells makes the important distinction between extra fat reserves and obesity (see also **Blackwell**). The IH as proposed provides no explanation for *obesity* (defined as extremely or pathologically high body weight). It offers an account of why food secure individuals might carry more body fat than food secure individuals, not of why anyone would have BMIs of 30 or 40. In a sense, we agree; we should strictly have titled our paper 'Food security as a driver of variation in body weight in humans'. Wells stresses that obesity results from systems having gone wrong (dysfunction), not the operation

of adaptive weight-regulation mechanisms. These kinds of debates often occur in the evolutionary medicine literature; how relevant is it to understand the normal function of the mood system in order to explain clinical depression, where the system has gone wrong (Nesse, 2000)?

Our response would be that many extreme cases of obesity no doubt involve metabolic dysfunction, but BMI in contemporary populations follows a continuous distribution with no point of discontinuity in it. Thus, it is not obvious exactly where normal (i.e. maladaptive but not arising from system dysfunction) responses to an evolutionarily novel environment end, and system dysfunction begins. In almost all studies, obesity is defined phenotypically using arbitrary BMI cut-offs. Thus, if food insecurity increases body weight over what it otherwise would be, then the proportion of individuals falling above the cut-off line will be higher under food insecurity than food security, wherever the line is set. This will be true regardless of whether metabolic pathology is present in the most obese individuals. Thus, a critical question for the relevance of the IH is whether social determinants like poverty and food insecurity are associated with a rightward shift in the whole distribution of body weights, in which case normally-functioning adaptive weight regulation mechanisms might be relevant, or the movement of a number of individuals from a healthy to a diseased mode of the distribution, in which case increased pathology is a more useful avenue of explanation.

Figure R1a plots the distributions of BMIs for adult women in the US (from the 1999-2004 National Health and Nutrition Examination Surveys [NHANES]), separated into high- and low-income households. (We are dividing by household income here rather than by food insecurity, as those were the variables immediately available to us. Given the strong association between income and food insecurity in the USA (Gundersen, Kreider, & Pepper, 2011), it is a reasonable conjecture that the pattern would be similar if we divided people into food-secure and food-insecure.) As figure R1a shows, the whole distribution of BMIs is shifted to the right in the low-income households. One simple mechanism producing this pattern would be an increase in body weight in poor women that applied multiplicatively (i.e. every low-income woman carries x% more weight than she would if rich). Figure R1b shows that such a shift is descriptively fairly accurate, by displaying the ratio of BMIs in poor as compared to rich households at each decile point in the distribution. Every decile point of the distribution is higher amongst the poor; that is, a woman in the thinnest 20% of poor women is heavier than a woman in the thinnest 20% of rich women. The proportionate increase is in the range 3-10% for each decile, and varies relatively little across the distribution. This is compatible with the meta-analytic evidence that food insecurity is associated with body weight regardless of whether the study uses mean BMI as the outcome variable, or the probability of exceeding a cut-off. It is also compatible with our observation that associations are stronger when the higher BMI cut-off of 30 is used compared to 25. If the hypothesised weight-shift is multiplicative, then it will increase the right-skew of the distribution and produce the largest absolute (not proportional) difference at the highest body weights.

Figure R1. Distribution of BMI amongst adult U.S. women, from the National Health and Nutrition Examination Survey (NHANES), 1999-2004, using the NHANES R package (Pruim, 2015). A. Density plot of BMI for women in high-income households (> 200% of Federal poverty line), and low-income households (\leq 200% of Federal poverty line). B. The ratio of BMI in low- and high-income households at each decile of the distribution. At every decile of the distribution, women from low-income households have higher BMI than their counterparts from high-income households.

One reading of this evidence, then, is that body weight is multiply determined, by factors including the food ecology, energy expenditure patterns, genetic variation, and the prevalence of metabolic or other pathologies, but cues of food insecurity also produce a proportionate increase in body weight (relative to not experiencing those cues). This would mean that problems of high and very high body weight would be exacerbated by food insecurity, even though food insecurity was not the sole shaper of the distribution. We absolutely accept such multiple determination must be at work, as we make clear in the target article. If food insecurity were the only driver, then, as **Lozano** points out, we should expect Western populations to have lower average adiposity than subsistence ones, which is clearly not the case. (On a related note, we find it strange that Lozano characterises us as dismissing the evolutionary mismatch hypothesis. We do not. We agree with him that the IH as we define it here is a variant of, not an alternative to, the evolutionary mismatch hypothesis. He compares us to a tobacco company denying the smoking-cancer link because not every smoker gets cancer. On the contrary, one can accept that smoking causes cancer, and still be interested in why some people are more vulnerable to the carcinogenic effects of smoking than other people are.)

A number of commentators suggest pathways by which weight regulation might become dysfunctional, through positive feedback between one component of the system and others, spiralling to the extremes of obesity (**Coppin, Blackwell, Davies et al**), or anorexia (**Nesse**). These positive feedback loops potentially explain the 'ratchet effect' mentioned by **Wells and Higginson, McNamara and Dall**, whereby individuals who are already overweight become more so over the long term. The existence of such ratchets may explain the right-skew of the distribution BMI in Western populations (Lang, De Sterck, & Abrams, 2016). However, the insurance principle is still relevant, since anything that causes the initial shift of body weight to the right will increase the probability of such positive feedback processes becoming established.

R6. The evidence base and alternative explanations for it

Lozano is technically incorrect when he says that only one out of six tests of the predictions of the IH using the food insecurity literature is significant. The single omnibus test at the heart of any meta-analysis—does the observed association differ significantly from zero in the whole dataset?—is significant in the current case, which is one out of one. However, we go on to show that gender and country income are strong moderators of the overall association. More broadly, though, we agree with **Lozano** that the evidence base we review is equivocal and problematic, and certainly does not offer emphatic support for the IH. There are two issues. First, although we offered some post-hoc speculations about why associations might be weaker in men (section 6.2), and in low-income countries (section 6.3), it would be much more convincing if there were *some* evidence that the insurance principle was at work in these contexts, even if the response were more subtle. Second, the significant correlational evidence that we found in women does not demonstrate causality; the association may indeed be explained by other processes or factors (**Boden and McCleod**). This is not unique to the food insecurity literature. Indeed, it is a problem for all of epidemiology. It is not sufficient, though, to opine that such processes or factors could exist. We need testable proposals for what they are. As such, we welcome **Hruschka and Han's** alternative account based on selection (lighter women end up into more food-secure households) rather than causation. This is indeed an alternative mechanism that could explain the distributions in figure R1. The selection account would seem to imply: (1) that the association between food insecurity and body weight would disappear when socioeconomic variables such as income are controlled for; and (2) that there should be no longitudinal prediction of weight gain by food insecurity, only a cross-sectional association. Our meta-analysis suggests that neither of these is the case. Nonetheless, Hruschka and Han's suggestion is a cogent one and the predictions of selection versus causation need to be rigorously tested with data.

Two developments are needed to improve the evidence base and make a more definitive determination on the value of the IH. First, the range of evidence considered needs to be broadened. Our meta-analysis was restricted to studies using the food insecurity questionnaires as predictors, and BMI as outcome. Such studies have a number of limitations, as discussed by **Nesse, Smith** and others. Broadening the scope to include more general measures of economic insecurity as predictors increases the range of available high-quality evidence substantially, as **Smith** points out in his valuable commentary. Crucially, this evidence is often longitudinal, and points to economic insecurity as a predictor of weight gain in men as well as women. Similarly, **Tapper** reviews evidence that children exposed to food restriction increase their food consumption, as the IH requires. Thus, although the evidence we meta-analysed does not find associations in children, there are other sources of evidence that the hypothesized response does exist. For non-Western societies, the food insecurity questionnaire-studies may find no average association, but there is evidence of fat reserves functioning to buffer seasonality and other forms of stochastic resource fluctuation in such societies (Wells, 2012a, 2012b). Indeed, Wells (2012b), on the basis of non-Western and paleontological evidence, specifically argues that the human tendency to store fat is a risk-management strategy for dealing with environmental fluctuation, which is the essence of the IH.

Second, the research designs need to become stronger, as **Boden and McCleod** point out. The food insecurity literature is dominated with cross-sectional studies that have limited value for investigating causality. As many of our commentators point out (**Dohle and Hofmann, Hruschka and Han, Mullan et al. Boden and McCleod**), we need more longitudinal evidence, which helps distinguish selection from causation. We also need instrumental-variable or natural-experiment studies. Examples could be policy changes affecting food insecurity that are introduced in one jurisdiction but not a neighbouring one, or exogenous events that expose some people but not others to temporary food restriction. These would allow better estimation of causal impact. Ultimately, we agree with **Cardel et al.** that randomized control trials are required to test the IH. Food stamps programmes may offer an opportunity here. U.S. food stamps programmes provide

monthly stamps allocations. Families tend to use these in the first three weeks of the month, producing a repeating cycle of consumption and hunger. Several studies have found that programme participation significantly predicts weight gain, including amongst men in some cases (reviewed by DeBono, Ross, & Berrang-Ford, 2012; Dinour, Bergen, & Yeh, 2007). Randomized control trials could compare the impacts of different programme designs leading to greater or lesser temporal variation in availability. The predictions of the IH are clear. Smaller-scale experiments would also be valuable; for example, micro-comparisons of eating behaviour after short-term experimental manipulation of perceived food insecurity would help demonstrate if there really is a causal pathway of the kind the IH requires (cf. Cardel et al., 2015).

R7. Assumptions and predictions of our formal model

Several commentators questioned the applicability of a theory and formal model based on birds to mammals like humans. To clarify, there is nothing about the insurance principle or the formal model we present in the target article that is specific to birds, or any more applicable to birds than mammals. The model is general. The best experimental tests happen to have been in birds, though as **Nesse** points out there is supportive mammalian evidence too. **Hill, Proffitt Leyva and DelPriore** argue that the model is too simplistic in not reflecting that one of the functions of fat stores is to fund reproduction. We agree that funding reproduction is an important function of adipose tissue, and moreover that sex differences in reproduction explain sex differences in adiposity. However, our model is not incompatible with this. All our formal model does is provide an algorithm for answering the question: if there is a given mapping between fat reserves and fitness in each time period, and a given probability of finding food in each time period, then what is the optimal amount of energy to consume and store? Although for ease of exposition we introduced our model by talking about the chances of surviving the time period, the model is actually agnostic about which factors determine the mapping between fat reserves and fitness. Survival, reproduction, and immunity could all contribute to setting the shape of the function shown in figure 1A of the target article. The model can be used to investigate the predicted effect of being a different sex simply by varying the shape of the mapping (section 6.2).

Hill et al. outline the need for models that explain why different taxa with different ecologies and lifecycles show different patterns of adiposity (and especially dimorphism in adiposity). We agree on the need for such models, but that is not what we were trying to do in this target article. In fact it is complementary. Our model takes as *input* a mapping between fat reserves and fitness, and gives as *output* an optimal eating policy. Other kinds of models are needed that give a mapping between fat reserves and fitness as their *output*, using features of the organism's ecology, biology and life history as the *input*, and thus making comparative predictions. Having said this, we agree with **Hill et al.** and **Chen** that another avenue for explaining the apparent sex difference in responsiveness to food insecurity is that cues of food insecurity, for women, might not only affect the reserves they need to store in order to execute a given reproductive strategy, but also affect what reproductive strategy they choose to execute. This deserves further investigation and formal modelling.

Wells suggests that the predictions of the model are falsified for humans, since the model predicts that those who are currently thinnest should gain weight, whilst those who are currently fatter should lose weight, whereas in human obesity, those whose body weights are highest to start with gain most over time. But this is to confuse long-term and short-term dynamics. Over the short-term, there is abundant human evidence that after a person's body weight is perturbed in either direction (for example, due to illness or experimental intervention), it returns fairly rapidly close to a pre-disturbance, individual-specific set point (Speakman et al., 2011). The short-term dynamics of human BMI distributions are dominated by regression to the centre; those with high BMIs lose weight whilst those with low BMIs gain weight (Lang et al., 2016). This is what our formal model predicts. What we need to explain is the inter-individual variation in what the set point is (and, relatedly, why the set point increases over time in some people). Here is where there is a role for chronic exposure to

environmental factors, including but certainly not limited to food insecurity. Wells is right that the long-term increases in individual set points appears to be proportional to existing BMI; this is what explains the right-skew of the BMI distribution in Western populations (Lang et al., 2016). This points to the importance of ratchet effects as discussed in section R5. Such proportionality does not arise in any obvious way from our formal model, or the other behavioural-ecological models on which we based ours. To explain them will require better understanding of the proximate mechanisms involved in weight regulation, the potential for positive feedback amongst such mechanisms, and the mismatch between current and ancestral environments. On this point we are in agreement with **Higginson, McNamara and Dall**, and with Wells (2012b).

R8. Concluding remarks

We take several lessons away from this exercise. The first is that you can think you have been clear, but find that others have taken you to mean something quite different from what you intended. This is a particular peril of interdisciplinary efforts, and seems to be acute whenever behavioural ecologists bring their arguments—which are based on a different level of analysis, and may use the familiar terms with different meanings—to the scholarly communities of psychology, biomedicine and public health. We are grateful to have had the chance to clarify some of these misunderstandings. Second, for a topic like obesity, there is more material to cover than can possibly be included in one article. Commentators were not shy in bringing this to light. In some cases, the additional material represents extensions and elaborations, and it is useful to be able to discuss these here. In other cases, we omitted evidence or distinctions that would have considerably improved our target article (broadened the evidence base, and averted some of the misunderstandings) had it been dealt with originally. We have highlighted some of these cases above. The third lesson is that to explain phenomena like obesity involves not just integrating multiple factors at the same level of the explanatory web, but multiple *levels* of factors (for example, information about the evolved function of weight-regulation mechanisms; about proximate psychological and physiological mechanisms; about pathology and dysregulation; about developmental influences; about contemporary food ecologies and the inequalities in them). Achieving this integration is extremely challenging, as the existence of poorly connected literatures in each of these different areas demonstrates; each of the literatures takes a different set of axioms and assumptions about relevance as its starting point. The variation in the commentaries shows this very clearly. Regardless of what value the IH as set out in our target article turns out to have, if any, we feel that the attempt to integrate these different kinds of information has been a valuable one.

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